

1 **Evidence demonstrating requirement of an intracellular signaling domain for accurate tumor cell**
2 **interactions with the host.**

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7 These experiments were based on measurement of total transcription following co-culture of cancer cells
8 with CAR T-cells. The evidence appeared to describe intrinsic differences in compensatory signaling
9 dependent on appreciation of some occurrence, event or structure at the membrane by the cancer cell that
10 is different in CAR T-cells.

11 Citations

12 1. Shah, N.N. and Fry, T.J., 2019. Mechanisms of resistance to CAR T cell therapy. *Nature reviews*
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15 Chai, L.Y., Le Bert, N. and Tan, N., 2024. Fratricide-resistant CD7-CAR T cells in T-ALL. *Nature medicine*,
16 30(12), pp.3687-3696.